
Quantifying Astrophysical Scattering With Transformers: Generic Mixture Density Network for FRB Analysis

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Abstract

The discovery rate of Fast Radio Bursts (FRBs) continues to increase with new radio facilities, yet extracting astrophysical parameters such as scattering timescale (τ) remains a significant bottleneck. Current approaches such as analytic template fitting and scattering-aware de-convolution are accurate but slow, initialization-sensitive, limited by low SNR, and require manual supervision. We present Multimodal Transformer Based Generic Mixture Density Network (**MT-GMDN**), which ingests FRB dynamic spectrum and timeseries through parallel transformer encoders, fuses their latent representations, and predicts the distribution of τ via a probabilistic mixture-density formulation that jointly handles the zero-inflated FRB population. Trained on $\sim 3,800$ FRBs from CHIME/FRB Catalog 2, MT-GMDN achieves $R^2 = 94\%$ on scattering regression and 90% recall for detection, while running $\sim 10^4 \times$ faster than classical fitting tools.

1 Introduction

Fast Radio Bursts (FRBs) are powerful extragalactic radio transients of millisecond duration (1). Propagation of the radiation through turbulent ionized interstellar and intergalactic media causes frequency-dependent temporal broadening modeled as a one-sided exponential tail with characteristic scattering timescale τ (2):

$$h(t) \propto \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta t}{\tau}\right), \quad \tau \propto f^{-4}, \quad I_{\text{obs}}(t) = I_{\text{int}}(t) * h(t). \quad (1)$$

Measuring τ has important astrophysical implications some of which include constraining plasma turbulence in host-galaxy environments (3; 4), diffuse halos (5), Milky Way ionized structure (6), and even cosmological parameters such as the Hubble constant (7). With detection rates reaching $\mathcal{O}(10^3 \text{ FRBs yr}^{-1})$, scalable automated inference is now essential. Current tools such as `fitburst` (8) and Monte Carlo Markov Chain (MCMC) based estimation (9), are accurate but slow, initialization-sensitive, and can fail for events characterized by low SNR or high radio frequency interference (RFI). Deep learning in FRB science has focused on classification (10; 11) and detection (12), leaving parameter estimation largely unexplored. In this work we present **MT-GMDN**, which is the first Deep Learning based regression framework that jointly estimates τ , its heteroskedastic uncertainty, and the probability of unresolved scattering in a single forward pass.

2 Methods

2.1 Probabilistic Formulation

Scattering timescales are strictly non-negative and empirically lognormally distributed (log-transforming τ on CHIME/FRB Catalog 2 (13) yields a near-Gaussian distribution). We model:

$$p(\tau | \mathbf{x}) = \text{Lognormal}(\tau | \mu(\mathbf{x}), \sigma^2(\mathbf{x})), \quad (2)$$

where location (μ) and scale (σ^2) parameters are estimated by a neural network. Since $>50\%$ of Catalog 2 bursts have unresolved scattering ($\tau < \tau_{\text{sampling time}}$), we extend Eq. 2 with a **Generic Mixture Density Network (GMDN)**:

$$p(\tau | \mathbf{x}) = p_0(\mathbf{x}) \delta(\tau) + (1 - p_0(\mathbf{x})) f_{LN}(\tau | \mathbf{x}), \quad (3)$$

where p_0 (Bernoulli parameter) is jointly learned with μ and σ (the parameters of the Lognormal f_{LN}) by minimizing cost function:

$$\ln p(\tau_i | \mathbf{x}_i) = \begin{cases} \ln p_{0,i}, & \tau_i = 0, \\ \ln(1 - p_{0,i}) + \ln \mathcal{N}(\ln \tau_i; \mu_i, \sigma_i^2) - \ln \tau_i, & \tau_i > 0. \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

This unifies detection and regression in one model, avoiding selection bias from discarding unresolved bursts. We also tested an alternative censored log-normal likelihood to handle unresolved cases reported as $\tau = 0$. Using the instrumental resolution limit, these samples were modeled as interval-constrained values ($0 \leq \tau_i < 0.98$ ms) contributing $\log F_{LN}(0.98 | \mu_i, \sigma_i)$ to the likelihood. However, this approach yielded highly unstable preliminary results, with predictions collapsing toward zero.

2.2 Model Architecture

The model architecture uses **two parallel transformer encoders** (Figure 1). The **Dynamic Spectrum Transformer** tokenizes two dimensional time frequency total intensity data $I(\nu, t)$ along time; each bin is a d -dimensional frequency embedding ($\mathbf{x}_{DS} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d}$), with 4-head self-attention over two encoder layers capturing temporal dependencies and frequency-dependent smearing. The **Timeseries Transformer** operates identically on the 1-D spectral-mean pulse profile derived from $I(\nu, t)$, focusing on asymmetric tail decay. Learnable positional embeddings outperform sinusoidal variants (14). Latent outputs $\mathbf{z}_{DS}, \mathbf{z}_{TS} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d}$ from the transformers are concatenated, linearly projected, then aggregated by attention-based temporal pooling into $\mathbf{h} \in \mathbb{R}^d$. Three linear heads predict p_0 (sigmoid), μ (linear), and σ (softplus). **Ablation** studies confirm the importance of multimodal fusion. Single-branch Transformer models substantially degraded performance on both observational and simulated test sets: the dynamic-spectrum-only model generalized poorly with negative R^2 , while the time-series-only model achieved only $\sim 72\%$ R^2 . A CNN encoder with a mixture-density regression head also underperformed, reaching only $R^2 = 45\%$ on the observational test set. These results show that both modalities are essential for robust scattering-timescale estimation architecture.

2.3 Data and Preprocessing

Training uses CHIME/FRB Catalog 2 dynamic spectra: 16,384 frequency channels (400–800 MHz), ~ 160 time samples at 0.983 ms. 64-channel block averaging reduces to 256 channels; spectra are independently min-max normalized to $[0, 1]$. Target τ from `fitburst` are log-transformed ($\tau' = \ln \tau$ for $\tau > 0$, else 0). No SNR filtering is applied. Timeseries are generated by collapsing the dynamic spectrum along the frequency axis via spectral averaging, producing a 1-D pulse profile with n time samples. Because a single repeating FRB source can exhibit variable scattering timescales (15; 16) and burst morphologies (11), we randomly split the CHIME/FRB Catalog 2 into training, validation, and test sets. We also generated a separate simulated data set specifically for testing.

3 Results

3.1 Performance on CHIME/FRB Catalog 2

Regression ($R^2 = 94\%$): MT-GMDN predictions correlate strongly along $y = x$ against `fitburst` at $\nu_{\text{ref}} = 400$ MHz. Constructed 95% CIs $e^{\mu \pm 1.96\sigma}$ capture the vast majority of catalogue values

Figure 1: **MT-GMDN Architecture.** Dual-branch parallel Transformer simultaneously extracts features from dynamic spectra and timeseries simultaneously. Features are concatenated, compressed via attention-based pooling, and decoded by three heads parameterizing the zero-inflated log-normal likelihood via p_0 , μ , and σ .

Table 1: MT-GMDN vs. MCMC on 50 simulated FRBs.

Metric	MT-GMDN (Lognormal)	MT-GMDN (Gamma)	MCMC	Target
RMSE (ms) ↓	7.62	6.67	7.83	Lower
R^2 ↑	0.71	0.73	0.69	Higher
Bias	-0.003	-0.98	-0.068	≈ 0
95% Coverage	1.00	0.97	0.89	≈ 0.95

with uncertainty scaling correctly with τ . The conditional median e^μ serves as the point estimate for robustness to the heavy-tailed lognormal. **Scattering Detection (AUC = 0.87):** At threshold $p_0 = 0.40$: **90% recall**, 76% accuracy, 63% precision. False positives relative to the Catalog 2 are physically motivated as catalogue $\tau = 0$ entries are lower limits, not true zeros.

3.2 Evaluating MT-GMDN Against fitburst and MCMC on Simulated Data

Broadband synthetic FRBs at constant fluence have SNR decreasing with τ . `fitburst` yields $R^2 = 39\%$, with many non-significant F-test p -values used to assess scattering significance over the non-scattering model, and poorly calibrated CIs. In contrast, **MT-GMDN achieves $R^2 = 68\%$** , contains all targets within the 95% CI, and produces uncertainties that scale appropriately with SNR (Figure 2). After training, MT-GMDN has $\mathcal{O}(1)$ inference complexity and achieves $\sim 10^4 \times$ speedup over `fitburst`. **Heteroskedasticity and Uncertainty Calibration:** Heteroskedastic behavior is confirmed by the Spearman correlation between predicted uncertainty σ and SNR: $\rho = -0.93$ ($p = 9.8 \times 10^{-18}$) for $\tau = 5$, ms and $\rho = -0.96$ ($p = 8.3 \times 10^{-23}$) for $\tau = 10$, ms. To assess uncertainty calibration, we fit 50 simulated FRBs using MCMC with a scatter-broadened pulse model (17), treating its credible intervals as the reference. The Lognormal MT-GMDN shows over-coverage for high-scattering and/or low-SNR events due to its inflated tail, while replacing Lognormal components with Gamma distributions improves calibration and outperforms both MCMC and the Lognormal formulation. Results are summarized in Table 1 and Figure 3.

4 Discussion and Conclusion

MT-GMDN redefines FRB scattering inference by mapping burst morphology directly to τ , bypassing classical fitting bottlenecks. Multimodal fusion enables stable Transformer training with limited

Figure 2: Comparison on low-SNR synthetic pulses. Marker size encodes relative SNR; colour encodes *fitburst* F-test p -value (left) and MT-GMDN scattering probability (right). MT-GMDN maintains calibrated CIs where *fitburst* fails.

Figure 3: Comparison of predicted scattering timescales with 95% confidence intervals for MCMC, MTGMDN-Lognormal, and MTGMDN-Gamma, the SNR decreases from 20 to 3 going left to right.

data, while the GMDN framework handles zero-inflated targets through a principled probabilistic formulation. The model identifies subtle asymmetries near the instrumental resolution limit and signals buried in noise from heavy scattering, where traditional tools can fail, while operating at $\sim 10^4 \times$ real-time speedup. However, modeling unresolved scattering with physically motivated likelihoods remains an open area for further research. Replacing the Lognormal mixture with a Gamma distribution mitigates heavy-tail over-coverage and yields better-calibrated confidence intervals, particularly for lower-SNR events. Beyond radio astronomy, the multimodal Transformer-GMDN framework offers a general template for probabilistic inference from low-SNR, limited-data time-frequency signals.

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